
Elpis

Release 0.93.08

Ben Foley, Nicholas Lambourne, Nay San

Dec 27, 2020

CONTENTS:

1	Installing Elpis with Docker	3
2	Installing Elpis on Google Cloud Platform	5
3	Getting started	7
4	Overview	9
5	Setup	11
5.1	Get some training files	11
5.2	Start Elpis	11
6	About the steps	13
7	Recordings	15
7.1	Add files	15
7.2	Select tiers	16
7.3	Prepare	18
8	Engine	19
9	Pronunciation Dictionary	21
9.1	Letter to sound rules	21
9.2	Pronunciation	22
10	Training sessions	25
10.1	Settings	26
10.2	Training	26
10.3	Results	27
11	Making a new transcription	29
12	More information about training files	33
13	Preparing files	35
13.1	Preparing your existing transcriptions	35
13.2	Clean your transcriptions by looking through them and checking the following:	36
13.3	Formats	37
14	Viewing Elpis training log file	39
15	Docker commands	41

16 Using the CLI Elpis Python API	43
16.1 Prepare your data	43
16.2 Run Elpis, train and transcribe	43
16.3 Notes	44
17 How to setup repositories to develop Elpis	45
17.1 Prepare your local dirs	45
17.2 Build the GUI	45
17.3 Mount local dirs into existing image.	45
17.4 Run the app	47
17.5 Monitor the app/code	47
18 API Documentation	49
18.1 elpis.endpoints package	49
18.2 elpis.engines package	49
18.3 elpis.transformer package	52
19 Indices and tables	53

Welcome! You've found your way to the documentation for Elpis. Elpis is a tool which allows language workers with minimal computational experience to build their own speech models for use in automatically transcribing audio. It relies on the Kaldi automatic speech recognition (ASR) library. Kaldi is notorious for being difficult to build, use and navigate - even for trained computer scientists. The goal of Elpis is to expose the power of Kaldi to linguists and language workers by abstracting away much of the needless technical complexity.

INSTALLING ELPIS WITH DOCKER

Elpis can be installed with Docker, a virtual computer running on **your** computer. To use this version of Elpis, you first need to install Docker.

Docker is a program which helps standardise the way we do computational tasks with data, regardless of the operating systems of all the people who might want to run those tasks. Rather than building separate code for Windows, Linux, Mac operating systems, we can write once and run it on a myriad of operating systems using Docker. For more information about Docker, view [Nay San's slides](#).

Follow the instructions on the [Docker site](#) to install Docker. You will need to create a (free) account with them to be able to download the Docker installer.

After you have installed Docker, start it. On a Mac, you will see a little whale icon in the top menu bar. On Windows you'll see a whale icon in the system tray.

With Docker running, we will use a **terminal** to install Elpis.

When you use an application like Elan or Word, you are using a 'graphical user interface (GUI)' to do stuff to your data via menus and buttons. Another way of interacting with your computer is via a terminal, also known as a command line or command prompt.

On Mac, open the *Terminal* app in your *Applications > Utilities* folder.

For Windows, open the search field in your taskbar, type `command` or `cmd` into it. Then, click or tap on the *Command Prompt* result to open it.

Download and run the Elpis Docker image by pasting this command in a terminal and pressing Return (or Enter).

```
docker run --rm -p 5000:5000/tcp coedl/elpis:latest
```


run

When you see a message about the server running, open `http://0.0.0.0:5000` in a browser.

```
bbb — exec bash — exec — bash — 79x11
bash-3.2$ docker run --rm -p 5000:5000/tcp coedl/elpis:online
* Serving Flask app "elpis" (lazy loading)
* Environment: development
* Debug mode: on
* Running on http://0.0.0.0:5000/ (Press CTRL+C to quit)
* Restarting with stat
* Debugger is active!
* Debugger PIN: 334-412-585
```

run

You should see the Elpis interface.

Elpis is a speech recognition tool, which you can use to transcribe audio. It works in four parts:

- Step 1) Add some language recordings and their transcriptions that you already have
- Step 2) Creating a pronunciation dictionary
- Step 3) Training the speech recognition "models"
- Step 4) Use it to transcribe new audio

Start by [making a new group of recordings](#) or [use one you have started before](#).

reset

run

With Elpis going, follow the steps in the [Elpis online workshop](#).

Docker

Docker

INSTALLING ELPIS ON GOOGLE CLOUD PLATFORM

Create an account at Google Cloud <https://cloud.google.com/>

When you have signed in, go to the [Getting Started](#) page. Set your country and agree to the Terms of Service, then press “Agree and Continue”.

You should land on the Console Home screen.

Make a new project using the CREATE PROJECT link. Later, you can create new projects from the “Select a Project” option in the blue top bar.

On the New Project screen, add a Project Name and press “Create”.

When the project has been created, the console will show the project’s Dashboard.

To add a server to the project, open the left side Navigation Menu and select “Compute Engine”. Then select “VM Instances”. If this is the first time your Google account has used Cloud Platform you may be offered a free trial! If so, go through the process of signing up for it. Otherwise, you may need to add billing details to access VM instances (TODO add more info about that). You will need to enter credit card details during the free trial opt-in process, but you won’t be billed unless you turn on Automatic Billing.

Now that your account has free trial or billing set up, the VM instances page should show “Create” and “Import” buttons.

Click “Create”

- Name it
- Select a Region and Zone
- Choose a machine size. The size will determine how much it will cost to run. The smallest vCPU instance on GCP is more than enough for the toy data set. That’s first series N1 with g1-small (shared-core machine type with 0.5 vCPU, 1.70 GB of memory, backed by a shared physical core). At training time CPU usage peaks at about 10% of the available compute on that instance type. For a bigger data set, or for faster training & transcription time, choose a faster machine.
- You may need to change the size of the boot disk if you expect to train with a large dataset.
- Select HTTP and HTTPS traffic in the Firewall options
- Click the “Management, security, disks, networking, sole tenancy” link.

Paste the following code into the “Startup Script” box

```
sudo apt update
sudo apt install -y apt-transport-https ca-certificates curl software-properties-
↳common
curl -fsSL https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu/gpg | sudo apt-key add -
curl -O https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu/dists/bionic/pool/edge/amd64/
↳containerd.io_1.2.2-3_amd64.deb
```

(continues on next page)

(continued from previous page)

```
sudo add-apt-repository "deb [arch=amd64] https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu_  
↳bionic stable"  
sudo apt update  
sudo apt install ./containerd.io_1.2.2-3_amd64.deb  
sudo apt install -y docker-ce  
sudo docker run -d --rm -p 80:5000/tcp coedl/elpis:stable
```

Then press “Create”

It will take approximately 15 minutes for the machine to start up and install all the software.

GETTING STARTED

OVERVIEW

The speech recognition process (also called speech to text) broadly involves steps of:

- Organising files that will be used to train the system
- Making pronunciation rules for your language
- Acoustic, pronunciation and language training

Then, using the trained system we can get a new transcription on un-transcribed recordings.

5.1 Get some training files

Start with downloading some files to use during the workshop. [Download the Abui files here](#). After the zip file has downloaded, unzip it to create a folder somewhere handy (for example, the Desktop).

5.2 Start Elpis

- We will provide a list of servers on the workshop day.
- Get an address from the list.
- If you are using Elpis in Docker on your own computer, the address will be `0.0.0.0:5000`
- Open a new web browser (Chrome or Firefox).
- Paste the address into the location bar.
- Press Enter/Return to start Elpis.
- When Elpis starts it looks like this.

Elpis is a speech recognition tool, which you can use to transcribe audio. It works in four parts:

- Step 1) Add some language recordings and their transcriptions that you already have
- Step 2) Creating a pronunciation dictionary
- Step 3) Training the speech recognition "models"
- Step 4) Use it to transcribe new audio

Start by [making a new group of recordings](#) or [use one you have started before](#).

reset

Welcome

On the Elpis welcome page, click on *making a new group of recordings* to go to the *New group of recordings* page.

ABOUT THE STEPS

There are four main steps in Elpis, with sub-steps in each.

1. Recordings
2. Pronunciation Dictionary
3. Training
4. New transcriptions

Recordings is where we collect and prepare the audio and text to train Elpis.

The **Pronunciation Dictionary** is where the system works out how the text words from the Recordings step are pronounced.

Training is where the “speech recognition models” are built.

New transcriptions is the place we go to use an existing training session to obtain a first-pass transcription on new audio.

RECORDINGS

We can do multiple sessions with Elpis. To keep track of which group of files we are using, give them a name here. For example, if you are using the Abui sample recordings, you could name this “Abui Recordings”. Then click Add New

The screenshot shows the Elpis web interface. At the top left is the Elpis logo, and at the top right is a 'reset' button. Below the logo is a sidebar menu with the following items: Recordings (selected), Files, Wordlist, Engine, Training (with sub-items Settings, Train, Results), and New transcriptions. The main content area is titled 'New group of recordings' and contains a form with a 'Name' field containing 'Abui Recordings' and an 'Add New' button.

files

New

7.1 Add files

On the *Add files* page, click inside the dotted area and go to where you downloaded the Abui files. Open the transcribed folder, select all the *wav* and *eaf* files and add them.

You can add additional words by uploading a wordlist in a plain text file named `additional_word_list.txt`, or a text corpus (with sentences) named `corpus.txt`. These are optional files. Words in either of these uploaded files will extend the pronunciation lexicon. Content in `corpus.txt` will also be used by the language model.

ELPIS reset

Recordings

Files

Wordlist

Engine

Training

Settings

Train

Results

New transcriptions

Add files

Current recordings: Abui Recordings

Upload your language recording and transcription files here.
Please use 44.1kHz WAV format audio, and .eaf Elan transcription files.
Audio files and transcription files need to have matching filenames.
You can also upload text files like wordlists or stories that don't have audio.

Upload or drop your files here

Import Settings

No Settings.

Add

files

7.2 Select tiers

Elan files can have multiple tiers for transcription, glosses, translations, etc. For training, we need to select the tier that contains the transcription text.

Elpis reads the Elan files you uploaded. The tier names and tier types from the files are shown here to choose from, or you can choose a tier by order - the top-most tier in all files would be selected by choosing 0, the second tier would be selected by choosing 1.

Just select one of the Tier options.

reset

Recordings

Files

Wordlist

Engine

Training

Settings

Train

Results

New transcriptions

Add files

Current recordings: Abui Recordings

Upload your language recording and transcription files here.
 Please use 44.1kHz WAV format audio, and .eaf Elan transcription files.
 Audio files and transcription files need to have matching filenames.
 You can also upload text files like wordlists or stories that don't have audio.

Upload or drop your files here

Uploaded files

abui_1.wav	abui_1.eaf
abui_2.wav	abui_2.eaf
abui_3.wav	abui_3.eaf

Import Settings

Tiers

Choose the tier that your transcriptions are on, just choose one of these.

Tier Type

Tier Name

Tier Order

Punctuation

Phrase

What to do with punctuation.

Replace these with spaces

Remove these

Cleaning

Remove text from annotations, add one per line.

Words to remove

Tags to remove

files

Add

7.3 Prepare

On the *Prepare* page we can see how Elpis has read your transcription files. If you have lots of training text there will be a delay while the text is prepared.

reset

Recordings

- Files
- Wordlist**

Engine

Training

- Settings
- Train
- Results

New transcriptions

Wordlist

Current recordings: Abul Recordings

Word frequency of training files

Word	Frequency
hekaai	2
dining	2
ayoku	2
kamar	2
mia	2
muila	3
deina	2
del	1

files

Prepare

ENGINE

Elpis is currently in development to support orthographic and phonemic transcriptions. For now, orthographic is the only option, but stay tuned for news about this!

In this step, choose “Kaldi” as the speech recognition toolkit/engine that Elpis will use. Kaldi is an orthographic speech recognition toolkit. Soon there will be other options here.

The screenshot shows the Elpis web interface. At the top left is the Elpis logo, which consists of a purple waveform icon followed by the word "ELPIS" in purple. To the right of the logo is a "reset" button. Below the logo is a sidebar menu with several sections: "Recordings" (containing "Files" and "Wordlist"), "Engine" (highlighted in purple), "Pronunciation" (containing "Letter to sound" and "Dictionary"), "Training" (containing "Settings", "Train", and "Results"), and "New transcriptions". The main content area is titled "Select Engine". It features a green box at the top that says "Current engine: kaldi". Below this is a dropdown menu with "kaldi" selected. At the bottom of the main content area is a "Next" button.

files

Prepare

PRONUNCIATION DICTIONARY

The Pronunciation dictionary is made so the system knows how words are pronounced. Elpis will make a rough draft for the words in the wordlist, based on a “letter to sound” file which you provide.

Like the recordings step, give this step a name. For example “Abui PD”

ELPIS

reset

Recordings
Files
Wordlist

Engine

Pronunciation
Letter to sound
Dictionary

Training
Settings
Train
Results

New transcriptions

Pronunciation Dictionary

No current pronunciation dictionary.
Make a new one, or select one from the list below.

Name Abui PD

select a group of recordings
Abui Recordings

Add New

Dictionary

Pronunciation

9.1 Letter to sound rules

The **letter to sound** file is a text file of rules mapping your orthography into phonemic transcription. It will be used to build a pronunciation dictionary.

It is formatted in two columns, space separated. Left column is all the characters in your corpus. The right column is a symbol representing the sound. You can use IPA or SAMPA for the right column. Comments can be written in the file with a # starting the comment line. For example,

```
# Abui  
j J  
f f  
s s
```

(continues on next page)

(continued from previous page)

```
h h
m m
n n
ng ■
r r
```

On Windows, use the free utility Notepad++ to convert CrLf to Lf in one go (Edit > EOL Conversion > Unix Format).

Upload the letter to sound rules `letter_to_sound.txt` from the Abui folder. Elpis will use this to build a pronunciation dictionary for the transcriptions you provided earlier.

The screenshot shows the Elpis web interface. At the top left is the Elpis logo. A 'reset' button is in the top right. The main content area is titled 'Upload Letter to Sound rules'. On the left is a sidebar with navigation options: Recordings (Files, Wordlist), Engine, Pronunciation (Letter to sound, Dictionary), Training (Settings, Train, Results), and New transcriptions. The main content area has a yellow box showing 'Current recordings: Abui Recordings' and 'Current pronunciation dictionary: Abui PD'. Below this is a text area with instructions: 'The letter to sound file is used to build a pronunciation dictionary for the corpus. Make one by listing one column of all the characters in your corpus. Make a second column (separated by a space) of a symbol representing how that character is pronounced. You can use IPA, or SAMPA for the pronunciation symbols. You can include comments in this file by beginning the comment line with #. For example: # This is a comment n n ng ŋ r r y j'. Below the text area is a 'Next' button. At the bottom of the main content area, a list of consonants is shown: # Consonants p p b b t t d d k k g g ? ? c C j J f f s s h h m m. The word 'Letter' is written to the right of the screenshot.

to sound

Letter

9.2 Pronunciation

Elpis uses the letter to sound file we uploaded to make a breakdown of how each word in our training files might be pronounced. You may need to correct some of them. After making corrections, press `save`. Press `reset` if you want to undo your changes and reset back to the rough draft.

If you notice characters in brackets e.g. (h), this indicates that the word includes a letter that is not covered in the letter-to-sound file. To correct this, add a letter to sound line in your letter-to-sound file for this letter, go back and make a new Pronunciation Dictionary, then upload the letter-to-sound file again.

ELPIS reset

Review the pronunciation dictionary

Current recordings: Abui Recordings
Current pronunciation dictionary: Abui PD

The pronunciation dictionary is generated from the wordlist and letter-to-sound rules you uploaded.

Characters surrounded by parenthesis were not found in your letter to sound map. Please add them, re-upload the l2s file and check the lexicon again.

```

!SIL sil
<UNK> spn
dining d I n I ŋ
deina d E I n a
di d I
mia m I a
hayei h a j E I
mulla m u I l a
kamar k a m a r
mui m u I
botol b 0 t 0 l
ba b a
ayoku a j 0 k u
homi h 0 m I
hada h a d a
dona d 0 n

```

reset save

Next

Lexicon

The !SIL and <unk> lines are used to handle silence and unknown words.

Check words that have been transcribed with consecutive matching characters. Do they represent one sound or two? If only one, add a line to your letter-to-sound.txt file, mapping the consecutive characters to a single symbol and rebuild the lexicon.

For example, if wunne is mapped to wunne w n n in the lexicon, then add nn n to letter-to-sound.txt, upload it again and rebuild the lexicon. The results should be collapsed lexicon entry wunne w n .

If your language has digraphs, put these earlier in the l2s, above single characters. For example,

```

ng ■
n n

```


TRAINING SESSIONS

Now our training files have been prepared, we can start a new training session. Give it a name then click Next.

The screenshot shows the ELPIS web interface. At the top left is the ELPIS logo, and at the top right is a 'reset' button. On the left side, there is a vertical navigation menu with the following items: Recordings (Files, Wordlist), Engine, Pronunciation (Letter to sound, Dictionary), Training (Settings, Train, Results), and New transcriptions. The 'Training' section is currently active. The main content area is titled 'Training' and contains a message: 'No current training session. Make a new one, or select one from the list below.' Below this message is a text input field for 'Name' with the value 'Abui Training'. Underneath is a section titled 'Select a pronunciation dictionary for this session' with a dropdown menu showing 'Abui PD (Abui Recordings)' and an 'Add New' button.

model

New

10.1 Settings

Here you can adjust settings which affect the tool's performance. A unigram (1) value will train the model on each word. A trigram (3) value will train the model by words with their neighbours.

The screenshot shows the 'Settings' page of the Elpis application. On the left is a sidebar with a purple header 'ELPIS' and a 'reset' button. The sidebar contains several sections: 'Recordings' (Files, Wordlist), 'Engine', 'Pronunciation' (Letter to sound, Dictionary), 'Training' (Settings, Train, Results), and 'New transcriptions'. The 'Settings' section is expanded, showing a yellow box with status information: 'Current recordings: Abui Recordings', 'Current pronunciation dictionary: Abui PD', and 'Current training session: Abui Training'. Below this is a text box explaining that settings adjust training. A dropdown menu for 'n-gram' is set to '1', with a tooltip explaining that a value of 1 sets the system to learn single words, while 2 or 3 includes neighbours. A 'Next' button is at the bottom.

Settings

10.2 Training

Got to the **Training** page to kick off the training process. Press *Start training* to begin.

The screenshot shows the 'Train' page of the Elpis application. The sidebar is identical to the 'Settings' page, but the 'Train' section is expanded. The 'Train' section shows a yellow box with the same status information as the 'Settings' page. Below this is a 'Settings' section with 'n-gram 1'. A status box shows 'ready'. At the bottom are 'Start training' and 'Next' buttons.

Ready

During training, we will see progress through the stages. You don't need to know what the terms here mean, they are speech recognition jargon words.

ELPIS reset

Recordings
Files
Wordlist

Engine

Pronunciation
Letter to sound
Dictionary

Training
Settings
Train
Results

New transcriptions

Train

Current recordings: Abui Recordings
Current pronunciation dictionary: Abui PD
Current training session: Abui Training

Settings
n-gram 1

training
Set up | complete
Prepare acoustic data | complete
Extract features | complete
Prepare language data | complete
Create language model | complete
Monophone training | in-progress
Triphone training | ready

Start training Next

Trained

10.3 Results

When training is complete, go to the Results page to see the results for this training session. These results tell us how the training went, and help us to understand what happened in the training process. These numbers are **scored** by comparing the words in one of the original transcriptions against the computer's version.

The results are:

- WER - Word Error Rate
- a word count
- INS - words that have been inserted (added)
- DEL - words that were deleted (missed)
- SUB - words that have been substituted (mistaken)

reset

Recordings
Files
Wordlist

Engine

Pronunciation
Letter to sound
Dictionary

Training
Settings
Train
Results

New transcriptions

Results

Current recordings: Abui Recordings
Current pronunciation dictionary: Abui PD
Current training session: Abui Training

WER 83.33	5 / 6	DEL 3	INS 1	SUB 1
-----------	-------	-------	-------	-------

Results

MAKING A NEW TRANSCRIPTION

Now the training has been done, on the **New Transcriptions** step, we can **Choose a file**. Upload the `audio.wav` file in the Abui untranscribed folder and click Transcribe.

The screenshot shows the ELPIS web interface. At the top left is the ELPIS logo, and at the top right is a 'reset' button. On the left side, there is a vertical navigation menu with the following items: Recordings (Files, Wordlist), Engine, Pronunciation (Letter to sound, Dictionary), Training (Settings, Train, Results), and New transcriptions (highlighted). The main content area is titled 'Transcribe some audio'. It features a green box with status information: 'Current recordings: Abui Recordings', 'Current pronunciation dictionary: Abui PD', and 'Current training session: Abui Training'. Below this is a dropdown menu labeled 'Select a model to use' with 'Abui Training' selected. A large dashed box contains the text 'Upload or drop an audio file here' and an 'Upload' button. Below the dashed box is a text input field containing 'Uploaded audio.wav' and a 'Transcribe' button. At the bottom of the main area is a status bar showing 'ready'.

transcription

New

Again, we see progress through the transcription stages, and more speech recognition jargon!

After the transcription is done, the transcription will show on the page, and the transcription can be downloaded in text or Elan format.

reset

Recordings
Files
Wordlist

Engine

Pronunciation
Letter to sound
Dictionary

Training
Settings
Train
Results

New transcriptions

Transcribe some audio

Current recordings: Abui Recordings
Current pronunciation dictionary: Abui PD
Current training session: Abui Training

Select a model to use Abui Training

Upload or drop an audio file here

Uploaded audio.wav

transcribed

- Extracting feature vectors | complete
- Creating model | complete
- Decoding (transcription) | complete
- Finding best path (transcription) | complete
- Adding word boundaries to FST | complete
- Converting lattice to CTM | complete
- Translating word indexes to words | complete
- Converting CTM to Textgrid | complete
- Converting Textgrid to ELAN | complete
- CTM output | complete

del del homi dong mui del del del dong hekaai ong dong ba del del di hada del del del del hada hada del del del hada del kamar del hekaai del dong del ong yaari del del dong del ong ong kaai ba kaai del di di hada del del hada del del dong del del del

Download

Download

Listen in Elan.

If you are using your own audio, rename the audio to `audio.wav`.

Elan

MORE INFORMATION ABOUT TRAINING FILES

The system trains with existing audio recordings and transcriptions. Generally, the more hours of training recordings you can train with, the better the results. However, it's not simply a matter of throwing everything you have into a bucket. Time spent cleaning and fine-tuning your existing transcriptions will have a good impact on your results.

You will typically get better results with few hours of files by using recordings from a common recording activity, e.g. short sentences, or stories, or word-repetition exercises.

For Elpis, the file format requirements are:

- a) WAV audio, preferably 44.1kHz mono but the system can convert stereo files and resample from different sample rates.
- b) Orthographic transcription of the audio. For today's workshop, the interface is using Elan transcriptions, soon we will be able to use text files.

We have other tools that will convert TextGrid and Transcriber files and will integrate this in the near future. Please let us know about your own file formats so we can include them in future versions!

- c) Filenames of the transcription must match the audio filename.

We are working on different ways to deal with this but for now, these are best done manually.

Transcriptions don't need to be word level. Annotations at an utterance/phrase level are fine.

Clean your transcriptions by looking through them and checking the following:

- Standardise variation in spelling
- Replace non-lexical number forms, shorthand forms and abbreviations with full lexical forms. For example, replace '9' with 'nine'.
- For more cleaning tips, see the [Data preparation](#) wiki page.

You can also add text files that contain words in the language, that don't have matching audio. These will be used to improve the system's language model.

PREPARING FILES

Speech recognition systems train on pre-transcribed speech data, building a statistical model of speech, which can then be applied to untranscribed speech. It is important to recognise that the type of speech that the system trains on will determine the type of speech that the trained model can be used on. For example if you train a system with speech of a person counting numbers, that model will be great for automatically transcribing more speech of that person counting, but wouldn't be practical for transcribing a different person telling stories.

Select a collection of data for which you have the most orthographically-transcribed, high-quality speech recordings. The system will learn from these to build a model for the language.

13.1 Preparing your existing transcriptions

Choose a set of data from your corpus. For maximum success in the workshop, use orthographically-transcribed content from a single speaker. Select data from a common recording activity, e.g. short sentences, or stories. The current version of Elpis uses Elan files. Let us know if you have other transcription file formats, as we are currently working on adding other transcription formats.

Duplicate your data set so that you don't affect your original data by preparing for this workshop, as some of the workshop steps are destructive.

Identify which Elan tier the transcriptions are on that you want the system to learn, and ensure that this "target" tier is named consistently across all the files in this corpus.

13.2 Clean your transcriptions by looking through them and checking the following:

- Reduce inconsistencies or typos in transcriptions.
- Standardise variation in spelling.
- Replace non-lexical number forms, shorthand forms and abbreviations with full lexical forms. For example, replace '9' with 'nine'.
- Code-switching in a single tier will confuse the system. Although it is possible to train a multi-lingual system, in this workshop we will focus on one language. Separate multiple languages by creating one tier for the language you want to train.
- Out-of-vocabulary words (words that are in the corpus but not in the lexicon) will reduce the accuracy. Ensure that everything in the speech signal is transcribed.
- Remove inline conventions such as speaker or language codes.
- Remove punctuation

13.3 Formats

As well as cleaning the transcription, ensure the audio is in a WAVE format.

Audio filenames should match the transcript filenames, bearing in mind that any commas, spaces, pipes, etc. in the filenames will cause problems. Rename your filenames to only use alphanumeric with underscores or dashes.

Use noise reduction techniques to clean the audio signal if needed.

You should now have a collection of cleaned transcriptions and audio in the right format.

For examples, refer to the [Abui toy corpus](#).

VIEWING ELPIS TRAINING LOG FILE

TODO: update paths for v0.94, the log is now in /state/model/HASH/run_log.txt

During the training stage a log file is written to /elpis/state/tmp_log.txt. Note that this file isn't created as soon as the Start Training button is clicked, there is a slight delay while some data prep is done. To view this file:

1. Run Elpis if it isn't already going.

```
docker run --rm -p 5000:5000/tcp coedl/elpis:latest
```

1. Open another terminal window and run this command to find the process ID of the elpis process. We'll use this to open another view into the same container.

```
docker ps
```

1. Should give results like:

CONTAINER ID	IMAGE	COMMAND	CREATED
↪ STATUS	PORTS	NAMES	
b5d2ec4a5ea3	coedl/elpis:online	"flask run --host 0..."	3 minutes ago
↪ Up 3 minutes	0.0.0.0:5000->5000/tcp	elastic_merkle	

1. Use the CONTAINER ID number to interact with the container. Replace CONTAINER_ID in the following command with whatever yours is, and run it.

```
docker exec -it CONTAINER_ID bash
```

1. Or use this one-liner: `docker exec -it $(docker ps -q) bash`
2. Look at the files in the /elpis/state directory.

```
ls /elpis/state
```

1. If tmp_log.txt file is there, you can look at it for some insight into what Kaldi is doing. We'll add some better feedback for knowing when this file is created soon.

```
tail -f /elpis/state/tmp_log.txt
```

There are stages during training which even this file appears to not give progress updates, particularly during the stage when the mfcc audio features are being generated.

DOCKER COMMANDS

The following commands can be executed in the **Terminal** (in Linux or MAC systems) or in the **Command Prompt** (in Windows systems), for managing Docker containers.

1. List the images that you have.

```
# docker images
```

1. Remove images.

```
# docker image prune -a
```

Verify that the images have been removed by running `docker images` again.

If the images are still there, you may need to remove stopped containers first, then re-run image prune.

```
# docker container prune
```

1. Save an image to USB. This command enables compressing the docker image as a tar file and saving it.

```
# docker save alpine > /path_to_the_usb_location/alpine.tar
```

1. Load a docker image from disk, after `cd` to where the image file is located

```
cd /path_to_the_usb_location/alpine.tar  
docker load -input alpine.tar
```


USING THE CLI ELPIS PYTHON API

Requires Docker.

16.1 Prepare your data

Make a local directory with

- letter to sound file
- your training data
- untranscribed audio file.

See example at <https://github.com/CoEDL/dev-corpora>

16.2 Run Elpis, train and transcribe

Start Docker.

Run an Elpis docker container, sharing your local recordings directory with the container.

```
docker run --rm -it -p 5000:5000/tcp -v ~/Desktop/recordings:/recordings --entrypoint ↪ /bin/bash coedl/elpis:0.94.0
```

In the container, run the Python training script. it will look in the folder you gave, and train a system based on the audio and text files it finds. We have a demo script you can try. Base your own training script on this example.

```
python examples/cli/elan/train.py
```

Use the trained model to transcribe some audio.

```
python examples/cli/transcribe.py
```

16.3 Notes

If you are developing Elpis, you can also mount a local copy of Elpis into the container. See the wiki for more details on the method of developing with VS Code.

```
docker run --rm -it -p 5000:5000/tcp -v ~/sandbox/elpis:/elpis -v ~/sandbox/elpis-  
→gui:/elpis-gui -v ~/Desktop/recordings:/recordings --entrypoint /bin/bash coedl/  
→elpis:0.94.0
```

Prepare for using the CLI. This installs Elpis as an operating system site package. Do this in the Docker container.

```
python3 -m venv venv  
source venv/bin/activate  
python setup.py develop
```

HOW TO SETUP REPOSITORIES TO DEVELOP ELPIS

This guide can assist in setting up directory structures to load repositories into a Docker container, enabling you to develop code and interact with the changes. This guide doesn't cover testing.

17.1 Prepare your local dirs

Get the repos for developing, `git pull` etc if you need.

```
mkdir ~/elpis-sandbox
cd ~/elpis-sandbox
git clone --depth=1 https://github.com/CoEDL/elpis.git
git clone --depth=1 https://github.com/CoEDL/elpis-gui.git
git clone --depth=1 https://github.com/persephone-tools/persephone
git clone --depth=1 -b elpis https://github.com/persephone-tools/espnet
```

17.2 Build the GUI

The Docker container has a build of the React app GUI in it, but if you are cloning the GUI repository and replacing the directory in the container with the local repository, the app build directory won't exist in the container (it is excluded from version control so it isn't in what you cloned). Run these commands to install the NPM libraries required, and to build a production version of the GUI into the `elpis-gui/build` dir. If you are developing the GUI, replace `npm run build` with `npm run watch` and then when you make changes to the GUI code, you'll get an automatic rebuild of the app. You will need to manually reload the browser that has the interface.

```
cd elpis-gui
npm install && npm run build
```

17.3 Mount local dirs into existing image.

Run the Elpis Docker image. Mount your local repositories into the container. Leave out the mounts you aren't actively developing. Thus you get to use the venv in the Docker container, don't need to set up your own, avoiding version issues.

```
docker run -it -p 5000:5000/tcp \
  -v ~/elpis-sandbox/elpis:/elpis \
  -v ~/elpis-sandbox/elpis-gui:/elpis-gui \
  -v ~/elpis-sandbox/espnet/egs/elpis:/espnet/egs/elpis \
```

(continues on next page)

(continued from previous page)

```
-v ~/elpis-sandbox/espnet/utils/:/espnet/utils/ \  
--entrypoint /bin/zsh \  
coedl/elpis:latest
```

17.3.1 CUDA (beta, for ESPnet).

If you have a CUDA-compatible GPU it is possible to achieve better performance by utilising the GPU in training your models. For this purpose, CUDA driver and runtime must be installed on host machine (more informations [here](#) and [there](#)):

Driver installation – if necessary (XXX is the version number):

```
sudo apt-get install nvidia-driver-XXX
```

Runtime installation (beware of distributions not yet supported...):

```
curl -s -L https://nvidia.github.io/nvidia-container-runtime/gpgkey | sudo apt-key_  
↪add -  
distribution=$(. /etc/os-release;echo $ID$VERSION_ID)  
curl -s -L https://nvidia.github.io/nvidia-container-runtime/$distribution/nvidia-  
↪container-runtime.list |\  
    sudo tee /etc/apt/sources.list.d/nvidia-container-runtime.list  
sudo apt-get update  
sudo apt-get install nvidia-container-runtime
```

Then you can try the CUDA-specific Dockerfile (gpu/Dockerfile in root folder):

```
cd ~/elpis-sandbox/elpis  
docker build . --file gpu/Dockerfile --tag coedl/elpis-cuda:latest > build.log
```

(It will write all logs in build.log file, because it is not so trivial to make it work flawlessly.)

Then, run it by adding the `--gpus all` argument in `docker run`:

```
docker run --gpus all -it -p 5000:5000/tcp \  
-v ~/elpis-sandbox/elpis:/elpis \  
-v ~/elpis-sandbox/elpis-gui:/elpis-gui \  
-v ~/elpis-sandbox/espnet/egs/elpis:/espnet/egs/elpis \  
-v ~/elpis-sandbox/espnet/utils/:/espnet/utils/ \  
--entrypoint /bin/zsh \  
coedl/elpis-cuda:latest
```

After, to be sure that CUDA mode for model training is enabled, check in the `elpis-sandbox/elpis/elpis/engines/espnet/objects/model.py` file that the command includes the `--ngpu x` (x is the number of GPUs) argument as:

```
p = run(f"cd {local_espnet_path}; ./run.sh --nj 1 --ngpu 1 &> {run_log_path}")
```

This feature is currently in a beta stage. Utilising the GPU for training is only currently recommended for those who know what they're doing or those particularly interested in achieving higher performance.

17.4 Run the app

Run these inside the container to install stuff.

```
source /venv/bin/activate
python setup.py develop
export FLASK_APP=elpis && flask run --host=0.0.0.0 --port=5000
```

You can also simply use the alias command inside the container.

```
run
```

17.5 Monitor the app/code

Open a new Terminal and get another window into the running Elpis container using this (this works on Mac, untested on PC)

```
docker exec -it $(docker ps -q) bash
```


API DOCUMENTATION

Information on specific functions, classes, and methods.

18.1 elpis.endpoints package

18.1.1 Submodules

18.1.2 elpis.endpoints.config module

18.1.3 elpis.endpoints.dataset module

18.1.4 elpis.endpoints.model module

18.1.5 elpis.endpoints.pron_dict module

18.1.6 elpis.endpoints.transcription module

18.2 elpis.engines package

18.2.1 Subpackages

elpis.engines.common package

Subpackages

elpis.engines.common.input package

Submodules

elpis.engines.common.input.clean_json module

elpis.engines.common.input.elan_to_json module

elpis.engines.common.input.make_prn_dict module

`elpis.engines.common.input.make_wordlist` module

`elpis.engines.common.input.resample` module

`elpis.engines.common.input.resample_audio` module

`elpis.engines.common.input.split_on_silence` module

`elpis.engines.common.input.textgrid_to_json` module

`elpis.engines.common.input.trs_to_json` module

`elpis.engines.common.objects` package

Submodules

`elpis.engines.common.objects.command` module

`elpis.engines.common.objects.dataset` module

`elpis.engines.common.objects.fsubject` module

`elpis.engines.common.objects.interface` module

`elpis.engines.common.objects.model` module

`elpis.engines.common.objects.path_structure` module

`elpis.engines.common.objects.pron_dict` module

`elpis.engines.common.objects.session` module

`elpis.engines.common.objects.transcription` module

`elpis.engines.common.output` package

Submodules

`elpis.engines.common.output.ctm_to_textgrid` module

`elpis.engines.common.output.textgrid_to_elan` module

`elpis.engines.common.utilities` package

Submodules

`elpis.engines.common.utilities.file_utilities` module

`elpis.engines.common.utilities.globals` module

`elpis.engines.common.utilities.hasher` module

`elpis.engines.common.utilities.json_utilities` module

`elpis.engines.common.utilities.logger` module

`elpis.engines.kaldi` package

Subpackages

`elpis.engines.kaldi.inference` package

Submodules

`elpis.engines.kaldi.inference.generate_infer_files` module

`elpis.engines.kaldi.input` package

Submodules

`elpis.engines.kaldi.input.json_to_kaldi` module

`elpis.engines.kaldi.objects` package

Submodules

`elpis.engines.kaldi.objects.model` module

`elpis.engines.kaldi.objects.transcription` module

Submodules

`elpis.engines.kaldi.errors` module

elpis.engines.persephone package

18.3 elpis.transformer package

18.3.1 Submodules

18.3.2 elpis.transformer.elan module

18.3.3 elpis.transformer.test_transformer module

INDICES AND TABLES

- `genindex`
- `modindex`
- `search`